

Enhancing Physical Properties of Recycled Paper Using Natural Pectin Extracted from Fruit Peel Waste

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Abstract

*The mechanical limitations of recycled paper remain a major challenge for its broader industrial application. This study investigated the potential of natural pectin extracted from fruit peel waste as a biodegradable reinforcing agent for recycled paper. Pectin was extracted from banana (*Musa paradisiaca*), orange (*Citrus sinensis*), and mango (*Mangifera indica*) peels using acid-assisted extraction methods under different extraction conditions. The extracted pectin was incorporated into recycled paper pulp at varying concentrations prior to sheet formation. Physical and mechanical characterization included tensile strength, tear resistance, folding endurance, grammage, and bulk density tests. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The addition of pectin significantly improved the mechanical properties of recycled paper. Tensile strength increased by 76.63%, tear resistance by 47.58%, and folding endurance by 17.07% compared to the control paper. Among the tested sources, banana peel pectin exhibited the greatest enhancement in tensile strength and tear resistance, while orange peel pectin improved paper compactness and flexibility. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in most parameters, with grammage showing the most significant change ($p = 0.000127$). These findings demonstrate that fruit peel-derived pectin has strong potential as an environmentally friendly reinforcement additive for recycled paper applications.*

Keywords: recycled paper, pectin, fruit peel waste, tensile strength, biodegradable additive

1. Introduction

The increasing demand for sustainable materials has intensified interest in recycled paper as an alternative to virgin paper products. Globally, paper consumption continues to rise due to increasing industrial packaging and printing demands, resulting in higher paper waste generation and resource consumption. In Indonesia alone, the pulp and paper industry required approximately 7 million tons of recycled paper annually as raw material in 2023 [3]. Recycled paper contributes significantly to waste reduction and resource conservation; however, repeated recycling processes reduce cellulose fibre quality, leading to inferior mechanical properties such as lower tensile strength, reduced tear resistance, and decreased durability [1],[2]. Previous studies reported that virgin paper possesses tensile strength values approximately 20.3% higher in the machine direction and 38.8% higher in the cross

direction compared to recycled paper [2]. These limitations restrict the broader utilization of recycled paper in applications requiring high mechanical durability.

The increasing accumulation of agricultural waste simultaneously creates environmental challenges and opportunities for biomass valorisation into functional biomaterials. In 2023, Indonesia produced approximately 9.34 million tons of bananas, 2.92 million tons of oranges, and 3.30 million tons of mangoes [12]. Considering that fruit peels may constitute approximately 40–50% of total fruit mass depending on the species, large quantities of peel waste are generated annually and remain underutilized. This condition highlights the strong potential for converting fruit peel waste into value-added biomaterials such as pectin-based reinforcement additives.

Various reinforcing additives have been explored to overcome the mechanical limitations of recycled paper. Synthetic additives such as polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) are widely used due to their effectiveness in enhancing inter-fibre bonding through hydroxyl interactions [4]. Nevertheless, synthetic polymers present environmental concerns because they are petroleum-based and contribute to carbon emissions during production [5]. Consequently, recent studies have focused on developing biodegradable and renewable reinforcing agents derived from natural materials.

Pectin is a naturally occurring complex polysaccharide commonly found in plant cell walls and agricultural waste, particularly fruit peels [6]. Due to its hydrophilic properties, film-forming ability, and abundant hydroxyl and carboxyl functional groups, pectin has demonstrated strong potential as a natural reinforcing material in cellulose-based systems [7], [8]. Hydrogen bonding between pectin and cellulose fibers is believed to improve inter-fibre adhesion and structural integrity [9]. In addition, pectin films possess favourable tensile modulus and flexibility characteristics that may improve stress distribution within paper matrices [10], [11].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The primary materials used in this study included recycled HVS paper, banana peels (*Musa paradisiaca*), orange peels (*Citrus sinensis*), and mango peels (*Mangifera indica*). Hydrochloric acid (HCl), citric acid, ethanol, and distilled water were used during the pectin extraction process. Experimental equipment included a blender, centrifuge, analytical balance, magnetic stirrer, oven, and an Arduino-based tensile and tear testing apparatus.

2.2 Pectin Extraction Procedure

Pectin extraction was performed using modified acid-assisted extraction methods adapted from previous studies [14]–[16]. Fruit peels were washed thoroughly, cut into small pieces, sun-dried for two days, ground into powder, and sieved using a 100-mesh screen.

Indonesia produces large quantities of fruit waste annually, especially from bananas, oranges, and mangoes, creating substantial potential for valorising fruit peel waste into value-added biomaterials [12]. National fruit production reached approximately 9.34 million tons for bananas, 2.92 million tons for oranges, and 3.30 million tons for mangoes in 2023 [12]. Since fruit peels may account for 40–50% of total fruit mass depending on the species, large quantities of organic waste are generated annually from fruit processing activities. Previous studies have primarily focused on food and biodegradable film applications of pectin, while comparative studies investigating pectin derived from multiple fruit peel sources for recycled paper reinforcement remain limited [13]. This gap highlights the importance of evaluating agricultural waste-derived pectin as a sustainable strengthening agent for cellulose-based materials.

Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the effect of natural pectin extracted from banana, orange, and mango peels on the physical and mechanical properties of recycled paper. The study also seeks to identify the pectin source that provides the greatest reinforcement effect on recycled paper performance.

Banana peel powder was extracted using 1.5% HCl at 80 °C for 120 minutes with continuous stirring. Orange peel powder was extracted using 0.5% HCl at 80 °C for 90 minutes, while mango peel powder was extracted using 7% citric acid at 90 °C for 150 minutes. The filtrate obtained after extraction was separated by centrifugation at 3500 rpm for 20 minutes. Pectin precipitation was carried out using ethanol for 24 hours, followed by filtration, drying, and grinding into fine powder.

The detailed extraction stages and treatment conditions for each fruit source are summarized in Figure 1, which presents the complete pectin extraction workflow used in this study.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the pectin preparation procedure from fruit peels. The extraction step is optimized according to fruit type. All filtrates are subjected to the same post-extraction and purification process.

The extraction workflow demonstrates that different fruit sources required distinct extraction conditions, including acid type, extraction temperature, and extraction duration. These differences were necessary due to variations in pectin composition and cell wall structure among fruit peels, which may influence extraction efficiency and final pectin characteristics.

2.3 Recycled Paper Fabrication

The recycled paper fabrication procedure consisted of pulp preparation, pectin incorporation, homogenization, sheet formation, pressing, and drying. Waste HVS paper was shredded and blended with water until homogeneous pulp was formed. Pectin was incorporated into the pulp at different concentrations before homogenization to ensure more uniform distribution within the cellulose matrix. The slurry was then moulded into paper sheets using a screen-based sheet formation technique, followed by pressing and drying [17]. The overall fabrication workflow is presented in Figure 2

2.4 Physical and Mechanical Characterization

Physical characterization included tensile strength, tear resistance, folding endurance, grammage, and bulk density measurements. Tensile strength testing was conducted using a custom Arduino-based tensile testing apparatus modified from ASTM D828 standards [18]. Tear resistance testing followed a modified ASTM D4533 trapezoidal tearing method [19]. Folding endurance was evaluated using the double-fold method based on ASTM D2176–97a [20]. Grammage measurements were performed according to ASTM D646 [21], while bulk density analysis followed TAPPI T500 standards. All treatments were tested in triplicate.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

Experimental data were analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to evaluate significant differences among treatments. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Recycled paper fabrication procedure.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of Pectin Addition on Recycled Paper Properties

The incorporation of natural pectin significantly affected the physical and mechanical properties of recycled paper. Mechanical performance improved substantially after pectin addition, particularly in tensile strength, tear resistance, and folding endurance. Tensile strength increased from 2.11 kN/m in the control paper to 3.28 kN/m in pectin-treated paper, while tear resistance increased from 0.376 N to 0.555 N. Folding endurance also improved from 1.79 to 2.10.

The improvement in mechanical strength is primarily attributed to enhanced inter-fibre bonding between cellulose fibres and pectin molecules. Pectin contains abundant hydroxyl (-OH) and carboxyl (-COOH) groups capable of forming hydrogen bonds with cellulose [9],[22]. These intermolecular interactions strengthen

fibre adhesion and improve stress transfer across the paper matrix. In addition, pectin may form thin flexible films between fibres, contributing to better stress distribution under mechanical loading conditions [10],[11].

Interestingly, grammage and bulk density showed slight decreases following pectin incorporation. Grammage decreased from 61.2 g/m² to 58.14 g/m², while bulk density decreased from 2.44 cm³/g to 2.29 cm³/g. This suggests that pectin reinforcement does not rely on increasing material mass but rather on improving the efficiency of the existing fibre network. The reduction in bulk density may indicate the formation of a more homogeneous and compact fibre structure with improved internal bonding.

These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that polysaccharide-based additives enhance recycled paper strength through hydrogen bonding and matrix densification mechanisms [23], [24]. Similar strengthening effects have also been observed in starch- and molasses-based reinforcement systems [25], [26]. As shown in Figure 3, the

improvements in tensile strength and tear resistance were substantially greater than the changes observed in grammage and bulk density, suggesting that pectin primarily enhanced the efficiency of inter-fiber bonding rather than increasing material thickness or mass.

Figure 3. Comparison of physical and mechanical properties between control and pectin-treated paper.

3.2 Influence of Pectin Source on Mechanical Performance

Different pectin sources exhibited distinct effects on recycled paper performance. Among the tested materials, banana peel pectin produced the highest tensile strength and tear resistance values, reaching 4.180 kN/m and 0.644 N, respectively.

The superior reinforcing performance of banana peel pectin may be associated with its relatively high galacturonic acid content and degree of esterification [27]. A higher galacturonic acid concentration provides more active carboxyl groups capable of forming hydrogen bonds with cellulose fibres, thereby increasing inter-fibre cohesion and tensile strength [28]. In addition, the molecular structure of banana-derived pectin may facilitate better film formation within the paper matrix.

In contrast, orange peel pectin exhibited the highest folding endurance and bulk density values. This behaviour may be related to its higher methoxyl content, which contributes to the formation of more elastic and flexible inter-fibre films [29]. Methoxyl groups reduce the rigidity of intermolecular bonding while improving flexibility and resistance to repeated deformation [30].

Meanwhile, mango peel pectin produced intermediate results across most parameters, indicating a more balanced but less pronounced reinforcing effect. Variations in molecular weight, branching structure, and esterification degree among pectin sources likely contributed to these differences in performance [6], [31].

Overall, these findings demonstrate that the physicochemical characteristics of pectin strongly influence its reinforcing behaviour in recycled paper systems. The comparative results summarized in Table 1 clearly show

that banana peel pectin consistently produced the highest tensile and tear resistance values, whereas orange peel pectin generated greater folding endurance and compactness characteristics.

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties of recycled paper based on pectin source.

Pectin source	Tensile strength test (kN/m)	Tensile resistance (N)	Folding endurance	Grammage (g/m ²)	Bulk density (cm ³ /g)
Mango	3.554	0.546	2.055	55.400	2.244
Banana	4.180	0.644	2.000	64.389	2.249
Orange	3.431	0.477	2.241	54.633	2.380

The data presented in Table 1 indicate that each pectin source contributed differently to paper performance, likely due to variations in molecular composition, degree of esterification, molecular weight, and galacturonic acid content. According to pectin structure theory, galacturonic acid residues and hydroxyl functional groups play important roles in forming hydrogen bonds with cellulose fibres, thereby influencing inter-fibre adhesion and mechanical strength [27],[28]. Pectin with higher galacturonic acid content may provide

stronger intermolecular interactions, which can explain the higher tensile and tear resistance observed in banana peel pectin treatments. In contrast, pectin with higher methoxyl content tends to form more flexible polymer networks, contributing to improved folding endurance and compactness characteristics [29], [30]. These findings suggest that pectin source selection may be tailored according to the intended functional application of recycled paper products

3.3 Statistical Analysis of Physical Property Changes

Statistical analysis confirmed that pectin addition significantly affected most measured parameters. ANOVA results showed statistically significant differences in grammage, tensile strength, tear resistance, and folding endurance ($p < 0.05$), whereas bulk density did not show a statistically significant difference.

Among all tested parameters, grammage exhibited the smallest p-value (0.000127), indicating the strongest statistical response to pectin incorporation. Although the reduction in grammage appears counterintuitive relative to the improvement in strength, this phenomenon may be explained by the ability of pectin to distribute uniformly between cellulose fibres without substantially increasing paper mass. The resulting fibre network becomes more efficient and mechanically reinforced despite lower overall mass per unit area.

The percentage increase analysis further demonstrated that tensile strength experienced the greatest enhancement, increasing by 76.63%, followed by tear resistance (47.58%) and folding endurance (17.07%). These trends are presented quantitatively in Figure 4, which illustrates the relative percentage changes observed after pectin incorporation. The figure demonstrates that mechanical strengthening effects were substantially more pronounced than density-related changes, indicating that pectin primarily functions as a reinforcing and bonding agent rather than a filler material.

Figure 4. Percentage changes in physical properties after pectin incorporation.

From a sustainability perspective, the successful utilization of fruit peel-derived pectin presents an environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic strengthening additives commonly used in paper manufacturing. The biodegradability and renewable nature of pectin make it highly suitable for sustainable recycled paper production and circular economy applications [32], [33].

In addition to improving mechanical strength, pectin incorporation may influence the microstructural arrangement of cellulose fibres. Uniform pectin distribution potentially fills micro voids between fibres, increasing contact area and improving fibre entanglement efficiency. This mechanism explains why significant improvements in tensile and tear resistance were achieved despite minimal changes in bulk density.

Future optimization studies involving pectin concentration, extraction conditions, and pectin characterization may further enhance recycled paper performance and industrial applicability. Furthermore, the ANOVA results summarized in Figure 5 indicate that grammage exhibited the strongest statistical response to pectin addition, suggesting that structural rearrangement within the cellulose network may be one of the dominant mechanisms underlying the observed mechanical improvements.

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.91158	9	0.10129	3.18929	0.01473	2.39281
Within Groups	0.63517	20	0.03176			
Total	1.54675	29				

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.63025	9	0.07003	2.93971	0.02137	2.39281
Within Groups	0.47643	20	0.02382			
Total	1.10668	29				

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	39.11943	9	4.346603	2.821107	0.025597	2.392814
Within Groups	30.81488	20	1.540744			
Total	69.93431	29				

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1023.755	9	113.7505	7.189844	0.000127	2.392814
Within Groups	316.42	20	15.821			
Total	1340.175	29				

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.494472511	9	0.054941	1.505255987	0.212974	2.392814
Within Groups	0.729993976	20	0.0365			
Total	1.224466487	29				

Figure 5. ANOVA results for all measured physical parameters.

The findings of this study suggest that fruit peel-derived pectin has potential to be further developed as a natural additive for recycled paper production. The increase in tensile strength and tear resistance indicates that pectin was able to improve bonding between cellulose fibres without requiring synthetic strengthening agents. Based on these results, recycled paper reinforced with natural pectin may have potential applications in simple packaging materials, craft paper products, or environmentally friendly paper-based materials.

Different pectin sources also produced different paper characteristics. Banana peel pectin showed stronger reinforcement performance, while orange peel pectin tended to improve flexibility and compactness. This observation suggests that the selection of pectin source could be adjusted depending on the intended use of the paper product. Future studies could explore combinations of different pectin sources to obtain a balance between strength and flexibility.

This study still has several limitations. The characterization focused mainly on physical and mechanical properties, while the chemical structure of the extracted pectin was not analysed in detail. Future research could investigate how factors such as extraction conditions, pectin concentration, and drying methods influence paper performance. Additional tests related to water resistance, durability, and surface properties may also help evaluate the feasibility of pectin-reinforced recycled paper for wider applications.

As agricultural waste is widely available in Indonesia, the utilization of fruit peel waste as a reinforcing material may also contribute to reducing organic waste while increasing the value of recycled paper products. Although this study was conducted on a laboratory scale, the results provide an initial reference for the development of more sustainable paper materials using locally available biomass resources.

4. Conclusion

Natural pectin extracted from fruit peel waste significantly improved the mechanical performance of recycled paper. Pectin incorporation increased tensile strength, tear resistance, and folding endurance through

enhanced hydrogen bonding and improved fibre network interactions. Among the tested sources, banana peel pectin exhibited the strongest reinforcing effect, particularly in tensile strength and tear resistance. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences in most physical parameters, with grammage showing the most pronounced change. These findings demonstrate the potential of fruit peel-derived pectin as a biodegradable and sustainable reinforcing additive for recycled paper applications.

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